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Assessment Of Facilities Management In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the “Assessment of Facilities Management in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria”. Two (2) objectives guided the study which includes; Assess the availability of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance, Katsina state; examine the management of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance, Katsina state. Two (2) research questions and research hypotheses were asked and formulated respectively to guide the study. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The total population for study is 1,507 comprised of 1,482 teachers, 25 quality assurance officials and 154 PTA officials. A multi stage sampling technique was adopted, the schools were divided into three clusters and three schools were selected from each cluster. Sample size of 306 was determined using Research Advisor sampling table. A proportionate sampling procedure was used to determine the distribution of questionnaires across the six schools sample. Instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated and the pilot tested using Cronbach’s Alpha technique, which revealed the reliability index of 0.89. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze the demographic data of the respondents while Mean and Standard deviations were used to analyze the research questions. One-Way-Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the two (2) null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The findings of the study reveal that, majority of the Teachers, Quality Assurance officials and PTA officials have similar opinion on the availability of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in the zone. ($p=0.89$); it also reveals that teachers, Quality Assurance officials and PTA shared a common opinion on the management of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in the zone ($p=0.356$) meaning that, all respondents agreed on the effectiveness of teaching facilities management. Based on the findings of the study it recommends that; there is the need for the Government to sustained adequate provision of teaching facilities in the public senior secondary schools in Katsina by carrying out need assessment on the schools and involving the community members and other philanthropies; there is a need for school management, quality assurance and PTA officials to maintain the effective management of teaching facilities by ensuring the implementation of preventive and routine maintenance of the facilities.

Keywords: Facilities, Management, Quality Assurance.

INTRODUCTION

The provision of Educational Facilities is the combined responsibility of the public and private sectors. Execution of educational programs demands that facilities are provided if success is to be achieved. Government, school proprietors, parents, and other stakeholders are expected to provide the facilities for their schools. The Federal Government posited that all stakeholders would be involved in every aspect of school management. This undoubtedly includes the provision of school plants. However, this aspect is one of the most neglected areas in the school system (Olagboye, 2019). As a result, there is a disparity in the provision of facilities from one school to another in urban centers, while schools located in rural areas are neglected. However, on the aspect of the utilization of school facilities in secondary schools, Adeboyeje (2018) stated that utilization is the degree or extent to which an item has been put into effective use. According to him, various degrees of utilization include non-utilization, under-utilization, maximum utilization, optimum utilization, and over-utilization. Non-utilization occurs when a facility is not put into use at all. When a facility is not used in its full capacity, underutilization occurs. There is over-utilization when a facility is used more than its capacity. These degrees of utilization constitute a waste of resources and are counter-productive. On the other hand, maximum utilization occurs when facilities are put into effective usage in line with the objectives. Optimum utilization occurs when facilities are used for many purposes by the school and members of the community; resources put into maximum and optimum usage are not wasted. They are likely to enhance the achievement of educational objectives.

The effective management of school facilities involves the alignment of asset planning and decision-making with educational priorities and strategies. Sound management across the facilities life cycle facilitates better decision-making about the acquisition, ongoing use or operation, and ultimately the disposal of assets at the right time, and in a cost-effective manner (Adeboye, 2017). When facilities are available and skillfully utilized, they influence learning and make it more meaningful. Tori (2019) noted that the availability of resources in a school boosts the morale of both teachers and learners towards effective delivery of lessons and is a major factor contributing to academic performance in the school system in senior secondary schools in Katsina state. The expectation for every school is to function in compliance with the goals and objectives of the national policy. To this end, students are expected to perform brilliantly in examinations which determine the quality of the output of schools (Osiji, 2020). However, this research focuses on assessing the management of school facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance, Katsina State.

Moreover, in a study conducted by Ekundayo (2022) reveals that the students achieved well in the affective and psychomotor domains of learning, the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between school facilities and students' achievement in the affective domain as well as a significant relationship between school facilities and students' achievement in the psychomotor domain of learning. Similarly Yakubu (2017) carried out a study on the evaluation of the provision and management of facilities in secondary schools in Zaria Education Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study among other things discovered that the provision and management of teaching facilities in secondary schools in Zaria Education Zone is very low especially on management of laboratories.

Statement of the Problem

In Katsina state, the quality of education remains a critical concern, with various factors contributing to the persistently low academic performance of students. Among these factors, the provision and effective management of school facilities play a pivotal role. Despite efforts by government and non-governmental organizations to improve educational infrastructure, many schools in the state still lack adequate classrooms, laboratories, libraries, and sanitation facilities. Where such facilities exist, their maintenance and management are often poor, resulting in environments that are not conducive to learning.

Objectives of the Study

- i. Assess the availability of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance, Katsina state.
- ii. Examine the management of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance, Katsina state.

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of the availability of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance, Katsina state?
- ii. What is the extent of the management of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance, Katsina state?

Research Hypothesis

HO₁. There is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on the availability of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal Education quality assurance

HO₂. There is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on the management of teaching facilities in public senior Secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The total population for study is 1,507 comprised of 25 secondary schools and this comprised of 1, 303 teachers, 25 quality assurance officials and 154 PTA officials. A multi stage sampling technique was adopted, the schools were divided into three clusters and three schools were selected from each cluster with sample size of 306 determined using Research Advisor Sampling table (2006). A proportionate sampling procedure was used to determine the distribution of questionnaires across the six schools sampled. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated and the pilot tested using Cronbach’s Alpha technique, which revealed the reliability index of 0.89. Descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard deviations were used to answer the research questions. One-Way-Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance.

RESULTS

The result was based on the 290 respondents who filled and returned their questionnaire.

Table 1.0: Opinions of Respondents on the Availability of Teaching Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance

S/N	Item Statements	Respondents	SA F	A F	D F	SD F	Mean	SD
1.	There are no enough classroom facilities in my school in Katsina	Teachers	110	49	26	21	3.21	1.02
		QA Officials	8	2	1	1	3.42	1.00
		PTA Officials	38	16	11	7	3.18	1.03
2.	Laboratories are not well equipped in my school in Katsina	Teachers	86	27	74	19	2.87	1.07
		QA Officials	6	2	3	1	3.00	1.08
		PTA Officials	36	7	27	7	3.00	1.10
3.	Chairs, tables are not provided my school.	Teachers	36	9	91	45	2.42	1.13
		QA Officials	6	1	4	1	3.00	1.13
		PTA Officials	35	8	24	5	3.01	1.05
4.	ICT centers are not provided in my school in Katsina	Teachers	139	29	23	15	3.43	0.94
		QA Officials	7	2	1	2	3.17	1.19
		PTA Officials	41	12	12	7	3.21	1.05
5.	Teaching aids like projectors, whiteboard is not provided in my school in Katsina	Teachers	65	24	86	31	2.59	1.09
		QA Officials	2	3	7	0	2.58	0.79
		PTA Officials	26	16	28	2	2.92	0.93
6.	My Schools has provision of teaching and learning facilities for students with special needs	Teachers	46	22	86	52	2.28	1.07
		QA Officials	2	3	7	0	2.58	0.79
		PTA Officials	27	17	19	9	2.86	1.02
7.	Sporting facilities are provided in my school in Katsina	Teachers	37	21	65	83	2.04	1.10
		QA Officials	0	3	8	1	2.17	0.58
		PTA Officials	27	16	15	14	2.78	1.15
8.	Library resource are provided in my school in Katsina	Teachers	39	10	51	106	1.91	1.15
		QA Officials	1	1	7	3	1.83	0.85
		PTA Officials	29	5	28	10	2.74	1.14
9.	Source of clean water for safe drinking are adequately provided in my school in Katsina	Teachers	30	16	62	98	1.89	1.06
		QA Officials	0	1	9	2	1.92	0.51
		PTA Officials	26	11	23	12	2.71	1.13
10.	Qualified teachers are adequately provided in my school in Katsina	Teachers	41	16	94	55	2.21	0.97
		QA Officials	3	2	7	0	2.67	0.89
		PTA Officials	22	12	28	10	2.64	1.07
Grand Mean			2.67					

Table 1.0 presents the analysis of data collected on the opinion of teachers, quality assurance officials and PTA officials on the availability and adequacy of teaching facilities on students' academic activities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance. The table further indicates the frequency counts, mean and standard deviation scores and it reveals that teachers has highest mean score of 3.43 in item four which indicates that this item was the most endorsed item by majority of the respondents. It was followed by quality assurance officials in item one with a mean score of 3.42, on the other hand quality assurance officials in item eight has the lowest mean score of 1.83 followed by teachers in item nine with a mean score of 1.89 which indicates that these items were the item most disagreed upon by majority of the respondents. The grand mean of 2.67 from the table is greater than the decision of 2.50 and this shows that majority of the respondents agreed that there is availability and adequacy of teaching facilities in Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State in Katsina zonal education quality assurance and that influence on the students' academic activities.

Table 2.0: Opinions of Respondents on the Management of Teaching Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance

S/N	Item Statements	Respondents	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD
			F	F	F	F		
1.	Enough classroom enhances learning activities in my school in Katsina	Teachers	147	23	19	17	3.46	0.97
		QA Officials	9	2	2	2	3.17	1.19
		PTA Officials	48	11	7	3	3.53	0.84
2.	Chairs, tables improve student activities in my school in Katsina	Teachers	147	26	21	12	3.50	1.90
		QA Officials	6	4	4	1	2.92	1.00
		PTA Officials	54	5	5	3	3.69	0.82
3.	ICT centers develop digital literacy in my school in Katsina	Teachers	120	36	37	13	3.28	0.97
		QA Officials	7	4	1	3	2.75	1.22
		PTA Officials	50	8	6	5	3.51	0.92
4.	Teaching aids like whiteboard influence teaching in my school in Katsina	Teachers	50	18	104	34	2.41	1.03
		QA Officials	3	2	9	1	2.58	1.00
		PTA Officials	26	7	34	2	2.88	0.99
5.	Provision of teaching facilities for student with special need enhance learning in my school in Katsina	Teachers	126	16	31	33	3.14	1.18
		QA Officials	2	3	2	8	2.17	1.19
		PTA Officials	30	10	8	21	2.76	1.31
6.	Availability of sport facilities improve learning in my school in Katsina	Teachers	38	19	62	87	2.04	1.12
		QA Officials	9	2	2	2	3.00	1.24
		PTA Officials	21	6	11	21	2.47	1.23
7.	Availability of library resource improve reading in my school in Katsina	Teachers	38	28	76	64	2.19	1.07
		QA Officials	3	1	10	1	2.50	1.00
		PTA Officials	24	22	7	16	2.79	1.14
8.	Qualified teachers influence the teaching learning in my school in Katsina	Teachers	38	34	92	42	2.33	1.00
		QA Officials	3	1	11	0	2.58	0.90
		PTA Officials	16	27	2	24	2.44	1.21
9.	Clean water for safe drinking influence the teaching learning in in my school in Katsina	Teachers	110	19	33	44	2.95	1.25
		QA Officials	8	3	2	2	3.00	1.13
		PTA Officials	32	4	13	15	2.89	1.23
10.	There is frequent routine maintenance in my school in Katsina	Teachers	13	7	108	78	2.78	0.19
		QA Officials	0	0	9	6	1.58	0.67
		PTA Officials	10	3	56	0	2.32	0.71
Grand Mean							3.42	

Table 4.3 presents the analysis of data collected on the opinion of teachers, quality assurance officials and PTA officials on the level of the management of teaching facilities and in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance. The table further indicates the frequency counts, mean and standard deviation scores and it reveals that PTA officials have highest mean score of 3.69 in item two which indicates that this item was the most endorsed item by majority of the respondents. It was followed by PTA officials in item one with a mean score of 3.53, on the other hand quality assurance officials in item ten has the lowest mean score of 1.58 followed by quality assurance officials in item five with a mean score of 2.17 which indicates that these items were the item most disagreed upon by majority of the respondents.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis one stated that, there is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on the availability of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal Education quality assurance.

Table 3.0: Summary of One Way ANOVA on the Availability of Teaching Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina ZEQA

Variation	Sum of Squares	Df.	Mean Square	F-ratio	Sig. (P)	Decision
Between Groups	10.209	21	.486	.635	0.891	Retained
Within Groups	205.046	268	.765			
Total	215.255	289				

P<0.05

Table 3.0 shows that variation between the groups is 10.209 and within the group is 205.046, the degree of freedom is 289 the mean square were .486 and .765. The f-calculated is .635 and the p-value is 0.891 which is greater than the level of significant (alpha) 0.05 hence the null hypothesis which stated no statistically significant difference in the opinion of Teachers, Quality Assurance officials and PTA on the availability of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal Education quality assurance is retained, meaning that teachers, quality assurance officials and PTA officials agreed on similar opinions on the availability of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina state.

Hypothesis Two:

Hypothesis two stated that there is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on the management of teaching facilities in public senior Secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance.

Table 4.8: Summary of One-Way ANOVA on the Management of Teaching Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina ZEQA

Variation	Sum of Squares	Df.	Mean Square	F-ratio	Sig. (P)	Decision
Between Groups	772.517	21	36.787	1.092	0.356	Retained
Within Groups	9029.359	268	33.692			
Total	9801.876	289				

P<0.05

Table 4.8 shows that variation between the group is 772.517 and within the group is 9029.359, the degree of freedom is 289 the mean square were 36.787 and 33.692 The f-calculated is 1.092 and the p-value is 0.356 which is greater than the level of significant (alpha) 0.05 hence the null hypothesis which stated no statistically significant difference in the opinion of respondents on the management of teaching facilities in public senior Secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance is retained. Meaning that teachers, quality assurance officials and PTA officials has similar opinion on the availability of teaching facilities on Students' in public senior secondary schools in Katsina state.

DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS

The study unveils that, there is no significant difference regarding the opinion of respondents Availability and adequacy of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality the finding is in line with that of assurance Yakubu (2017) who discovered that there is no significant difference regarding the opinion of respondents on the provision and management of teaching facilities in secondary schools in Zaria Education Zone is very low especially on management of laboratories. This finding also buttresses the assertion of Ekundayo (2022) on the relationship between school facilities and students' achievement and the study revealed that the schools' physical facilities were not all that adequate. The study further revealed that the students achieved well in the effective and psychomotor domains of learning. The study revealed that there was a significant relationship between school facilities and students' achievement in the affective domain as well as a significant relationship between school

facilities and students' achievement in the psychomotor domain of learning. From the foregoing the researcher asserted that for effective management of secondary schools to be achieved there is the need for adequate provision of facilities in both quantity and quality.

The study also reveals that there is no significant difference regarding the opinion of respondents on the Effective management of teaching facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal education quality assurance, this findings agrees with the findings of Umar and Samuel (2019) who conducted a study on the influence of school facilities and types on Senior Secondary School Science Students' academic performance in Nasarawa State, Nigeria and the study found that there was a significant influence of school facilities on science students' academic performance in urban and rural schools and also, there was a significant influence of school facilities on science students' academic performance in private and public schools. At this juncture the researcher declares that effective utilization of teaching facilities promotes learning and effective management of secondary schools.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that there is availability and management of teaching and learning facilities facilitates in public senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal quality assurance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the research findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were raised:

1. There is the need for the Government to sustained adequate provision of teaching facilities in the public senior secondary schools in Katsina by carrying out need assessment on the schools and involving the community members and other philanthropies.
2. There is a need for school management, quality assurance and PTA officials to maintain the effective management of teaching facilities by ensuring the implementation of preventive and routine maintenance of the facilities.

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